

Understanding Precipitation Trends for Valsad District, Gujarat

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Abstract

The precipitation studies are very useful for understanding distribution pattern and variation and also for understanding the characteristics of climate change. The study is principally focused on trend analysis of precipitation time series data of 30 years (1973-2002) using Mann-Kendall test at 85%, 90% and 95% significant level and Sen's Slope Estimator Method at 95% of significance level for 17 Stations of Valsad district of Gujarat from June to October months. The results shows that total 9 stations among 17 show the presence of significance of monotonic trend of precipitation in which at all stations, rainfall is declining in each month (June to October) except Jhuj which shows rising of rainfall in June month over a study period (1973-2002).

For broad understanding of variability of precipitation at each station, the box plot of rainfall is plotted for each month (June to October). In June, Dugri and Valsad, in July, Mandva, in August, Mandva and Bopi, in September, Kalvada and in October, no stations are associated with large dispersion of rainfall. Also, Pindval shows higher outliers in June and October. Madhuban is associated with higher outlier in June, July, Septembers and October. Nanivahiyal and Varolitalat are having greater outliers in Septembers.

Keywords: Boxplots, Climate Change, Precipitation, Mann-Kendall Test, Sen's Slope Estimator, Trend analysis.

Introduction

The increasing level of greenhouse gases (GHGs) due to direct/natural or indirect anthropogenic source in earth's atmosphere might be associated with climate change of different portions of the world. Various studies specify that a significant rise in global temperature would be expected as the repercussion of doubling of carbon dioxide (CO₂)⁹. Climate change is reviewed as serious threat to decisive management of natural resources and obstacle in progression from poverty to prosperity³. Two main climatic variables which are used to analyze the effect of climate change in region are temperature and rainfall¹². Water is core of sustainable development and stability of any country.

In India, the major sources of water are ground water and surface water (river and glacier melt from Himalayan). The availability, distribution and quality of these resources are projected to affect the higher temperature and extreme

weather conditions which result in the severe impacts on both urban and rural regions⁶. The rainfall discrepancy is key incentive for national economy. In India, for agriculture sector, the main resource is rainfall although the appreciable amount of water flows.

Approximately more than half of population of India relies upon agriculture for their living⁶ which successively depends on one of the monsoon precipitation and it is trending⁴. In India, the uneven distribution of water supply might be one of the key issues faced by water resource management due to natural (temporal/spatial) pattern of rainfall and further this variability in rainfall is emphasized by climate change¹¹.

Rainfall is the main parameter that regulates the hydrological cycle. For any region, the changes in the pattern of rainfall directly influence the water resources of that region⁸. The impact of climate change on water resources has received much attention from regional to global scale. The analysis of long period rainfall record gives information about rainfall patterning and fluctuations. Problems corresponding to flood, drought and allocation of water are as per different demand and policies. It is prime concern in any hydrological system to study the historical hydrological trend of that system which further leads to predict the future trends¹². Apparently, in India, remarkable trend of rainfall has been found out in monsoon (June-October) on a regional scale¹.

The present study focuses on determining monthly trend of rainfall for past record of monsoon season at 17 stations of Valsad district of Gujarat State in India for 30 years during 1973-2002. There are many studies carried out on trend detection in climatological and hydrological time series for all over the India as well as on regional basis and also for particular river or river basin in India.

In such studies, mostly the parametric and non-parametric methods such as Mann-Kendall test and Kendall test were used for detection of trends. The non-parametric methods are considered as more advantageous over a parametric method because it does not depend upon distribution of time series of particular records.

In some studies, the Mann-Kendall test has been considerably used as self-sufficient method for identification of trend of rainfall and temperature data³. In present study, the Mann-Kendall test is used to analyses the statistical significance of the trend (or to identify the presence of the monotonic trend of time series) and Sen's slope estimator is

used to determine the magnitude of trend in time series and boxplots are carried out for better understand the rainfall variability at each station for month of June to October ⁸.

Material and Methods

Study Area: Valsad, one of the important tribal district of Gujarat state, located in the southern part of Gujarat State is having total geographical area of 3055 sq. km (Fig. 1) and is situated between north latitude of 20°07' to 20°45' and east longitude of 72°43' to 73°29'. The Valsad district is bounded by Navsari District from north and northeast and in east and south by Nasik district of Maharashtra. The western boundary is formed by Arabian Sea. According to 2011 district census data of valsad district, the decadal growth in population of district from 2001 to 2011 is 21%.

Also, the results of demographic analysis show the rapid growth in urban population during last two decays. Valsad district consists of good potential of water resources as area consists of perennial river system of Par, Wanki, Damanganga, Varoli and Auranga rivers with the associated tributaries. For industrial and domestic water supply, the canal network is also utilized.

Valsad district is situated in south of tropic of cancer, falls under heavy rainfall area of south Gujarat, having sub-tropical climate with moderately high humidity. The major amount of rainfall in the Valsad district is received during the period from June to October from the south-west monsoon with total rainy days approximately range from 40 to 55 days/year. The total yearly rainfall of Valsad district is around 1626 mm which is approximately 79% of annual rainfall⁷.

Data and Methodology: In present study, the historical rainfall records of 17 rain gauge stations of Valsad district for 30 years from 1973-2002 are statistically analyzed. The

daily rainfall data for the 17 rain gauge stations were obtained from State Water Data Centre (SWDC), Gujarat. The daily rainfall data are summed up to get total monthly rainfall data for month of June to October for study period (30years, 1973-2002). By applying simple arithmetic average method, all the data gaps were filled for all 17 stations. Further to understand the nature of trends, non-parametric methods, Mann-Kendall test and Sen's Slope estimator are used.

To check the presence of monotonic trends in time series the Mann-Kendall test is applied and for estimating the true change of rainfall per month, Sen's Slope Estimator method is applied from month June to October and for all stations and for further understanding of skewness of rainfall at each station, the boxplots for each month (June to October) are plotted.

The rain gauge stations selected for study are tabulated (Table 1). The Overall methodology adopted is shown in the form of flow chart in fig. 2.

Trend Analysis: Assessment of system changes over a significant period of time by applying various empirical methods can be defined as trend analysis of time series. The purpose of trend analysis is to identify the rising or declining of random variable over a time period. For trend analysis, parametric and non-parametric tests are used. Generally, the non-parametric test assumes that the data do not follow specific distribution hence, in parametric test, it is necessary to assume any underlying distribution (frequently normal distribution). In present study, the non-parametric tests namely Mann-Kendall test and Sen's Slope estimator test are used.

Details of the Mann-Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator test are briefly described by Bera¹⁰.

Fig. 1: Location Map of Valsad District

Table 1
Rain Gauge Station selected for study in Valsad, Gujarat

Stations	District	Latitude	Longitude
Bildha	Valsad	20.571	73.463
Bopi	Valsad	20.597	73.351
Dhamni	Valsad	20.436	73.267
Dharampur	Valsad	20.537	73.175
Dungri	Valsad	20.687	72.951
Hanmatmal	Valsad	20.560	73.338
Jhuj	Valsad	20.735	73.419
Kalvada	Valsad	20.642	72.978
Madhuban Dam	Valsad	20.218	73.044
Mandva	Valsad	20.352	73.186
Par @ Nani-Vahiyal	Valsad	20.454	73.158
Panchalai	Valsad	20.477	73.062
Pardi	Valsad	20.504	72.949
Pindval	Valsad	20.478	73.356
Vadoli	Valsad	20.205	73.400
Auranga @ Valsad	Valsad	20.631	72.933
Varoli-Talat	Valsad	20.189	73.131

Fig. 2: Flowchart Describing Overall Methodology

Results and Discussion

Trend Analysis: The presence of trend and the magnitude of trend are carried out using the Mann-Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator method respectively for the time series (1973-2002) for all the 17 stations of Valsad district for monsoon months (June- October). There are three confidence

interval; 85%, 90%, 95% are considered for the MK test and 95% confidence interval is considered for the Sen's slope estimator.

At 85% of Confidence Interval: Among all the 17 stations, for June month, two stations namely Dhimmi and Juju are having statistically significant monotonic trend. The rainfall is declining at Dhimmi and rising at Juju. In July month, only Panchalai station shows significant monotonic trend of rainfall in which the rainfall is reducing over a study period. In august month, six stations Bhilda, Bopi, Hanmatmal, Jhuj, Nanivahiyal and Panchalai are having statically significant monotonic trend. At all these six stations, the rainfall is reducing over a study period. In September month, among all 17 stations, no station shows significant monotonic trend of rainfall. In October, three stations Dharampur, Mandva and Panchalai show significant monotonic trend of rainfall and rainfall is declining in all of the three stations.

At 90% of Confidence Interval: In June month, at only one station Jhuj, the monotonic trend of rainfall is present, also the rainfall is rising at Jhuj station. Panchalai is the only station which shows that the monotonic rainfall trend is present for July month and also rainfall is falling off over a steady period. In month of September, no stations among all 17 stations shows significant monotonic trend. Two stations Mandva and Panchalai show the significant monotonic trend of rainfall with reducing rainfall in October.

At 95% of Confidence Interval: All stations show no trend of rainfall in month of June, July and Septembers at this significant level. Panchalai station shows significant monotonic rainfall trend in August and October months. In both months, the rainfall is declining over a period of time (1973-2002).

The monthly time series of rainfall changes over a time period (1973-2002) is shown in figures 3 to 11 for Bildha,

Bopi, Dhamni, Dharampur, Hanmatmal, Jhuj, Mandva, Nanivahiyal and Panchalai stations respectively.

Fig. 3: Rainfall Trend at Bhilda Station for JJASO

Fig. 4: Rainfall Trend at Bopi Station for JJASO

Fig. 5: Rainfall Trend at Dhamni Station for JJASO

Fig. 6: Rainfall Trend at Dharampur Station for JJASO

Fig. 7: Rainfall Trend at Hanmatmal Station for JJASO

Fig. 8: Rainfall Trend at Jhuj Station for JJASO

Fig. 9: Rainfall Trend at Mandva Station for JJASO

Fig. 10: Rainfall Trend at Nanivahiyl Station for JJASO

BoxPlots: The Box plot gives the broad view of central data and is very useful for data analysis by showing the central

tendency and dispersion in addition with possible outliers with graphical skewness of data series in single graph⁵. The

box plots are plotted for all 17 stations for each month from June to October for rainfall to understand the rainfall variability and pattern at each station as shown in figures 12 to 16.

The results show that in June month, the Dugri and Valsad are associated with large dispersion in rainfall having almost zero skewness but Madhuban and Pindval stations are having greater outliers. In July month, the Mandva station shows larger variation of rainfall then other stations, having little positive or upward skewness but Madhuban station is associated with higher outliers. Mandva and Bopi stations

are associated with higher dispersion of rainfall in month of august with almost perfectly symmetric about median but Nanivahiyal and Varoltalat stations consist of higher outliers.

In September month, Kalvada station consists of higher and negative (downward) skewness of rainfall but higher outliers are associated with Madhuban station. There is very negligible dispersion associated in October month for all stations but Hanmatmal, Madhuban and Pindval stations are consist of higher outliers.

Fig. 11: Rainfall Trend at Panchalai Station for JJASO

Fig. 12: Box plot of rainfall for June month

Fig. 13: Box plot of rainfall for July month

Fig. 14: Box plot of rainfall for August month

Fig. 15: Box plot of rainfall for October month

Fig. 16: Box plot of rainfall for October month

Conclusion

The proposed study on station wise rainfall data from June to October month of 17 stations of entire Valsad district from 1973-2002 using Mann-Kendall test and Sen’s Slope estimator methods and plotting of boxplots station wise for each month (June to October) focused on to have clear understanding about rainfall trend over Valsad district. Among the 17 stations, the significant monotonic trend of rainfall is presented at 9 stations. Rainfall declines over a study period (1973-2002) in each month (June to October) except Jhuj station. In June month, rainfall is rising over a study period (1973-2002) at Jhuj. In June at Dugri and

Valsad, in July at Mandva, in August at Mandva and Bopi, in Septembers at Kalvada and in October at no stations, large dispersion of rainfall is observed. Pindval station is associated with higher outliers in June and October month even though it is far away from coast.

Madhuban station is having higher outliers in June, July, Septembers and October month. It might happens because the station is in the near proximity of Par River. Nanivahiya and Varolitalat stations are associated with greater outliers in boxplot in September month. Both stations are in near proximity of Waki and Par River respectively. At a time

when climate change is an accepted phenomenon, change in the rainfall pattern can change the rainfall runoff relations for the region.

The city of Valsad is at a strategic location on the golden quadrilateral connecting Mumbai and Ahmadabad. It is prone to flood almost every year in the last decade. It was therefore important to establish this climate change for Valsad to understand the change in the annual and monthly rainfall patterns. This study can be helpful for further development of rainfall modeling and future rainfall prediction which can help the policy makers for efficient water management and distribution as per the change observed in rainfall due to climate change.

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